

Sol-gel based hybrid coatings for corrosion protection of AA2024-T3 alloys

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ABSTRACT

Hybrid sol-gel coatings were synthesized and studied in the present work as pre-treatments for the aluminum alloy AA2024-T3 to provide corrosion protection in 0.05 M NaCl solution. The pristine sol-gel films were prepared from Tetraethoxysilane (TEOS) and 3-glycidoxypropyl-trimethoxysilane (GPTMS) precursors. The coatings synthesis protocol was further developed by incorporation of graphene nanosheets and colloidal SiO₂ nanoparticles with the aim of improving the structural properties such as coating integrity and barrier properties against corrosive medium. To this end, graphene nanosheets were modified through a straightforward hydrothermal approach which resulted in compatible and stable dispersion of nanosheets into GPTMS/TEOS sols (Fig.1). Additionally, the hybrid sols were doped with colloidal SiO₂ (Ludox) nanoparticles to achieve dense and defect free structures. Optimization of sol synthesis was based on the results of ATR-FTIR and UV-vis-NIR spectroscopies. Opening of epoxy rings and completion of hydrolysis and condensation reactions during the synthesis process were also confirmed. Coatings were characterized through thickness, water contact angle, and electrochemical properties (potentiodynamic polarization).

Fig. 1. (a) FTIR spectra of pristine GPTMS/TEOS (GT, black curve), GPTMS/TEOS doped with graphene nanosheets before chemical modification (GT/GN-phys, blue curve) and GPTMS/TEOS doped with chemically modified graphene nanosheets (GT/GN-chem, red curve) and (b) visual image of dispersion improvement of graphene nanosheets in GPTMS/TEOS sols after chemical modification.

The results showed that the incorporation of graphene nanosheets into hybrid sol-gel coatings affected the corrosion properties. According to surface chemical, structural and electrochemical characterizations, incorporation of chemically modified graphene nanosheets into TEOS and

GPTMS sols including colloidal SiO₂ led to the better corrosion protection properties compared to those with graphene nanosheets embedded in pure TEOS and GPTMS sols. The coatings based on chemically modified graphene and SiO₂ nanoparticles appeared to be thicker (thickness = 5.5 ± 0.2 μm) and rougher (average roughness = 7.4 ± 0.1 nm) with reduced hydrophilicity (water contact angle = 74 ± 2 °). According to polarization measurements, promising passive (barrier) ranges were formed for such coatings and corrosion current densities decreased down to values almost $\sim 10^5$ times smaller than that of the bare AA2024-T3 alloy (Fig.2). Such encouraging barrier properties could originate from the both layered graphene structure and the presence of SiO₂ nanoparticles that likely reduced the active surface area of the coating accessible for the attack of the corrosive medium through perhaps reinforcing the cross-linking density. These coatings could be promising candidates to be applied on the surface of AA2024-T3 alloys combined with deposition of an organic top coat for corrosion protection applications.

Fig. 2 (a) Potentiodynamic polarization curves of bare AA2024-T3 alloy (black curve) and samples coated with hybrid sol-gel coatings including GPTMS/TEOS doped with chemically modified graphene nanosheets (GT/GN-chem, red curve), GPTMS/TEOS/colloidal SiO₂ (GTS, grey curve) and GPTMS/TEOS/colloidal SiO₂ doped with chemically modified graphene nanosheets (GTS/GN-chem, purple curve) and (b) visual images of corroded surface areas (white dashed circles) after exposure to corrosive medium (0.05 M NaCl). For a better visibility, the white lines indicate the boarder between the coated and uncoated areas. As it is visible to the naked eye, the sample with GTS-GN-chem coating shows the least surface damage compared to the bare alloy.

Keywords: Aluminum alloy, Sol-gel coatings, Corrosion protection, Barrier properties, SiO₂ nanoparticles, Graphene nanosheets

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